

Access to information in public archives: From theory to practice in the archive of the University of Coimbra, Portugal

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Abstract

Archives have always been a fundamental resource for the State, institutions and citizens. In these information systems and services (Gomes, 2019), the availability of any information support for consultation always depends on two elements: legal authorisation and the existence of archival finding aids (International Council on Archives, 2000). This study analyses the current archival legislation in Portugal, regarding access to information in public archives, and describes its applicability in the Archive of the University of Coimbra (AUC). The methodology adopted comprised the analysis of the legislation and a case study (Stake, 2005; Yin, 2014). The AUC is “the depository of the invaluable documentation produced and received by the University”. As a service, it was created organically in 1901 and, as an information system, it dates to 1290, the year that the king D. Dinis created the "Studium Generale", today the oldest University in Portugal. It also integrates the documental resources of the Coimbra District Archive, created in 1931 (Archive of the University of Coimbra, 2022a, b). The current legislation in Portugal determines the limits on the access and communicability of archival information, namely the following legal diplomas: Decree-Law No. 47/2004 and Act No. 26/2016. All documentation in the AUC is available to any citizen since the general principle of Free Access to documentation in public archives applies. However, we must point out the limitations on the access to certain documentation, resulting from the need to guarantee the preservation and conservation of the originals. In these circumstances the user is referred to the consultation exclusively in digital format, which is the case of the Catholic Church records - 1459-1911 (baptisms, marriages, and deaths), created by parishes in the district of Coimbra. At the AUC there are communicability restrictions on documentation from the following fonds: Criminal Police, Forensic Medicine and Notarial Archives (wills). All in all, this study allowed us to identify limitations to the communicability of

information on which there are legal restrictions due to the existence of personal data, nominative data, and compliance with certain legal deadlines. Therefore, knowledge of the applicable legislation is essential for the information professionals / archivists.

Keywords: access to information, public archives, archive of the University of Coimbra.

Background and purpose of the research

Archives have always been a fundamental resource for the State, institutions and citizens. In these information systems and services (Gomes, 2019), the availability of any information support for consultation always depends on two elements: legal authorisation and the existence of archival finding aids (International Council on Archives, 2000). Information Professionals / Archivists are responsible for promoting the widest possible access to archival materials, they should “respect the privacy of individuals who created or are the subjects of records” and must “act within the boundaries of relevant legislation” (International Council on Archives, 1996). This research analyses the current archival legislation in Portugal, regarding access to information in public archives, and describes its applicability in the Archive of the University of Coimbra (AUC).

Research methods and instruments

The methodology of this research comprised the analysis of the legislation and a case study (Stake, 2005; Yin, 2014). A search was carried out on the AUC institutional website and a structured interview was conducted with its director. The interview consisted of six questions on the following themes: access and communicability to the fonds, reproduction of documents with the camera of mobile phones in the AUC reading room.

Findings and discussion

The AUC is “the depository of the invaluable documentation produced and received by the University”. As a service, it was created organically in 1901 and, as an information system, it dates to 1290, the year that the king D. Dinis created the "Studium Generale", today the oldest University in Portugal. It also integrates the documental resources of the Coimbra District Archive, created in 1931, which is associated to the AUC (Archive of the University of Coimbra, 2022a, b). The current legislation in Portugal determines the limits on the access and communicability of archival information, namely the following legal diplomas: Decree-Law No. 47/2004, of March 3, and Act No. 26/2016, of August 22. According to Decree-Law No. 47/2004, article 10 - "The documentation incorporated under this diploma will be made available for public consultation in accordance with the current laws, namely article 17 of Decree-Law No. 16/93, January 23". Act No. 26/2016, article 44, determined an amendment to Decree-Law No. 16/93, of January 23, the legal diploma that establishes the general regime of archives and archival heritage, already previously amended by Act No. 14/94, of May 11, and Act No. 107/2001, of September 8. The article 17 mentioned above is replaced by the following: "1 - Access to documentation held in public archives is guaranteed, subject to the limitations arising from the imperatives of preservation of species, and the restrictions arising from the general and special legislation on access to administrative documents shall apply. 2 - Documents containing nominative data shall be accessible: a) 30 years after the date of death of the persons to whom the documents refer; or b) if the date of death

is not known, 40 years after the date of the documents, but not before 10 years have elapsed from the moment of knowledge of the death. 3 - Sensitive data concerning legal persons, as defined by law, may be communicated 30 years after the date of extinction of the legal person, if the law does not stipulate a shorter period". In the AUC, all documentation is available to any citizen since the general principle of Free Access to documentation in public archives applies. However, we must point out the limitations on the access to certain documentation, resulting from the need to guarantee the preservation and conservation of the originals, in which case the user is referred to the consultation exclusively in digital format. For example, that is the case of the Catholic Church records - 1459-1911 (baptisms, marriages and deaths), created by parishes in the district of Coimbra. At the AUC there are communicability restrictions on information from the following fonds: Criminal Police, Forensic Medicine and Notarial Archives (wills). In the AUC Reading Room, the respective regulation applies, according to the provisions of Act No. 31/2019, of 3 May, which regulates the use of digital devices for personal use and allows "digital reproduction, in images, of documents from the fonds and collections". Thus, at the AUC "the reader may use personal digital equipment to photograph documents privately, without flash and in silent mode, provided that the respective equipment(s) are registered" (Archive of the University of Coimbra, 2021).

Conclusion

We conclude that the communicability of information may condition public accessibility to documentation. The study carried out allowed us to identify limitations to the communicability of information on which there are legal restrictions due to the existence of personal data, nominative data, and compliance with certain legal deadlines. Therefore, knowledge of the applicable legislation is essential for the information professionals / archivists.

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ACCESS TO INFORMATION IN PUBLIC ARCHIVES FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE IN THE ARCHIVE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF COIMBRA, PORTUGAL

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BACKGROUND

Archives are a fundamental resource for the State, institutions and citizens. In these information systems and services the availability of any information support for consultation depends on two elements: **legal authorisation** and **the existence of archival finding aids** (International Council on Archives, 2000). Information Professionals / Archivists are responsible for promoting the widest possible access to archival materials, they should "respect the privacy of individuals who created or are the subjects of records" and must "act within the boundaries of relevant legislation" (International Council on Archives, 1996). This research aims to **analyse the current archival legislation in Portugal, regarding access to information in public archives, and to describe its applicability in the Archive of the University of Coimbra (AUC).**

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The AUC is **"the depository of the invaluable documentation produced and received by the University"**. As a **service**, it was created organically in **1901** and, as an **information system**, it dates to **1290**, the year that the king D. Dinis created the **"Studium Generale"**, today the oldest University in Portugal. It also integrates the documental resources of the Coimbra District Archive, created in 1931, which is associated to the AUC (AUC, 2022a, b). Current legislation in Portugal that determines the limits on the access and communicability of archival information:

- Decree-Law No. 47/2004, of March 3
- Act No. 26/2016, of August 22

According to Decree-Law No. 47/2004, article 10 - "The documentation incorporated under this diploma will be made available for public consultation in accordance with the current laws, namely article 17 of Decree-Law No. 16/93," Act No. 26/2016, article 44, determined an amendment to Decree-Law no. 16/93, of January 23, the legal diploma that establishes the general regime of archives and archival heritage. The article 17 is replaced by:

- 1 - Access to documentation held in public archives is guaranteed, subject to the limitations arising from the imperatives of preservation of species, and the restrictions arising from the general and special legislation on access to administrative documents shall apply.
- 2 - Documents containing nominative data shall be accessible: a) 30 years after the date of death of the persons to whom the documents refer; or b) if the date of death is not known, 40 years after the date of the documents, but not before 10 years have elapsed from the moment of knowledge of the death.
- 3 - Sensitive data concerning legal persons, as defined by law, may be communicated 30 years after the date of extinction of the legal person, if the law does not stipulate a shorter period."

Artigo 44.º
Alteração ao Decreto-Lei n.º 16/93, de 23 de janeiro
O artigo 17.º do Decreto-Lei n.º 16/93, de 23 de janeiro (Estabelece o regime geral dos arquivos e do património arquivístico), alterado pelas Leis n.ºs 14/94, de 11 de maio, e 107/2001, de 8 de setembro, passa a ter a seguinte redação:

«Artigo 17.º
1 - É garantido o acesso à documentação conservada em arquivos públicos, salvas as limitações decorrentes dos imperativos de conservação das espécies, aplicando-se as restrições decorrentes da legislação geral e especial de acesso aos documentos administrativos.
2 - São acessíveis os documentos que integrem dados nominativos:
a) Desde que decorridos 30 anos sobre a data da morte das pessoas a que respeitam os documentos; ou
b) Não sendo conhecida a data da morte, decorridos 40 anos sobre a data dos documentos, mas não antes de terem decorrido 10 anos sobre o momento do conhecimento da morte.
3 - Os dados sensíveis respeitantes a pessoas coletivas, como tal definidos por lei, são comunicáveis decorridos 30 anos sobre a data da extinção da pessoa coletiva, caso a lei não determine prazo mais curto.
4 -

Act No. 26/2016 August 22, art. 44°, that changes art. 17° of Decree-Law No. 16/93, of January 23

Digital representation of Catholic Church records in 1903

METHODOLOGY

Analysis of the legislation and a case study (Stake, 2005; Yin, 2014). A search was carried out on the AUC institutional website and a structured interview was conducted with its director on the following themes: access and communicability to the fonds, reproduction of documents with the camera of mobile phones in the AUC reading room.

Available to any citizen since the general principle of **Free Access** to documentation in public archives applies.

Limitations on the access to certain documentation, resulting from the **need to guarantee the preservation and conservation of the originals** - the user is referred to the consultation exclusively in digital format. For e.g., the case of the Catholic Church records - 1459-1911 (baptisms, marriages, and deaths), created by parishes in the district of Coimbra.

There are **communicability restrictions** on documentation from the fonds: Criminal Police, Forensic Medicine and Notarial Archives (wills).

Digital representation of Estatutos Pombalinos da Universidade de Coimbra

In the AUC Reading Room, the regulation applies, according to the Act No. 31/2019, of 3 May, which regulates **the use of digital devices for personal use** and allows **"digital reproduction, in images, of documents from the fonds and collections"**.

"The reader may use personal digital equipment to photograph documents privately, without flash and in silent mode, provided that the respective equipment(s) are registered" (AUC, 2021).

AUC online research portal - <https://pesquisa.auc.uc.pt>

CONCLUSION

Communicability of information may condition public accessibility to documentation. Limitations to the communicability of information on which there are legal restrictions due to the existence of personal data, nominative data, and compliance with certain legal deadlines. Knowledge of the applicable legislation is essential for the Information Professionals / Archivists.

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Photo n.º 1 - by the authors - AUC building entrance